

USE OF RESOLE SEPIOLITE-PHOSPHATE NANOCOMPOSITE FOR BUILDING FACADES

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Introduction

- Recent serious fires → i.e. Grenfell Tower fire (UK, 2017) and the Lacrosse Building fire (AU, 2014) → Increasing need for innovative façade materials which meet both structural and fire safety requirements
- Nanocomposite materials → Superior properties
- Phenolic resins → Excellent performance at high temperatures

- Sepiolite-phosphate → 3D rigid structure during the thermal treatment
- Resol/SepP nanocomposite → Proposed to be used with glass fibers as a prospective alternative for building facades cladding
- This study focus is on formation of phosphate nanoparticles and dispersion of the SepP (3%, 5%, and 10%) in the phenolic resin

Figure 1. Grenfell tower fire in London

Methods

No	SepP	Phenolic resin	Catalyst
1	-	100%	5%
2	3%	100%	5%
3	5%	100%	5%
4	10%	100%	5%

Results

Figure 2: Micrograph of SepP composite:

Figure 3. SepP (3%)-PR nanocomposite

Figure 4. SepP(5%)-PR nanocomposite

Figure 5. SepP(10%)-PR nanocomposite

Conclusions & future directions

- The investigation of SepP in the phenolic resin has been carried out for the first time in this research. HIM showed that the SepP nanopowders formed effectively and phosphate nanoparticles uniformly covered the surface of sepiolite fibers.
- Different contents of SepP in the phenolic resin have been investigated and SEM micrograph showed that 3% of SepP had a better dispersion in the nanocomposite.
- The next step will be high shear mixing of resole-SepP nanocomposite to prevent agglomeration and make a uniform dispersion. The proposed phenolic nanocomposite will be used with 3D glass fibers to make a 3D GFRP nanocomposite and fire tests will be conducted to validate performance requirements of the façade system.

References

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Acknowledgments

